

3 MIC: minimal inhibitory concentration. BP: MIC breakpoint, which is defined as the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial necessary to inhibit visible growth. ¹MIC breakpoints established by the Clinical & Laboratory
4 Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines (CLSI, 2018a and 2018b). ²MIC breakpoints established by the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST, 2019). Values in bold indicate intermediate
5 resistance to that antimicrobial. Values in bold and red indicate resistance to that antimicrobial. Swab: nasal swab. NA: not available. Dashes indicate values not tested for the indicated antimicrobial.